

Effects of Noise Pollution on Mental Health in Pakistan

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Ashir Azim Tunio**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: ashirazim7@gmail.com

⁽²⁾**Ahmed Yar Khan**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: ahmed.yar082@gmail.com

⁽³⁾**Neiha Imran**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: nanyimran@hotmail.com

⁽⁴⁾**Muhammad Umair Barry**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: Takziniteanimations@outlook.com

⁽⁵⁾**Haya Afeef**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: hayasadiq.s@gmail.com

⁽⁶⁾**Dr. Masood Hassan**

PhD, IoBM, Karachi, Pakistan and Visiting Faculty Greenwich, Karachi, Pakistan,
Email: masoodhassan1@hotmail.com (Corresponding Author)

Abstract

The environmental risk posed by noise pollution and the impact it has is attracting increasing attention around the world. In addition to the effects, it has on the human auditory system, noise pollution has also been linked to a wide range of problems related to stress as well as other heart conditions. According to the most recent study conducted by the WHO, more than approximately 1.5 million lives are lost every year as a direct result of the noise that is caused by traffic. A significant portion of it is associated with other conditions such as sleep disorders, mental stress, unchecked hormonal fluctuation, heart rate, and blood pressure. There is a connection between all of these factors and cardiovascular diseases. Other issues include the onset of a wide variety of psychological problems, as well as substance abuse issues, such as excessive use of alcohol and tobacco. Other problems include the use of harmful substances. There is a significant connection between the nervous pathways in the body and dysfunction caused by noise in the environment. Because of this, there is a significant relationship between being exposed to noise and various nervous disorders as well as other problems.

Keywords: Mental Health, Depression, Stress/anxiety & Noise Pollution

Introduction

In today's modern society, noise pollution has emerged as one of the most widespread causes of environmental stress. Noise can have major effects on the physiology and behavior of people, which can have a negative impact on their health and well-being. These effects include discomfort during activities, disturbed sleep, cognitive difficulties, stress and mental disorders, hearing problems, and an increased risk of heart diseases (Lercher, 1996, Passchier-Vermeer & Passchier, 2000, Paunović et al., 2009, Stansfeld et al., 2000, Basner et al., 2014). Studies conducted by scientists over the course of the last few decades have provided abundant evidence that noise pollution can have serious negative effects on people's physical health over the course of their lifetimes (Davies & Van Kamp, 2012, Pirrera et al., 2010). However, mental health or psychological effects have not received that much attention and the results are mixed due to the fact that noise exposure assessments and statistical model variables are both involved. (In terms of the evaluation of noise exposure, the majority of the earlier studies used modelled noise maps, such as Sound PLAN or SonBase, to estimate the population-based noise exposure at the residential location (Sørensen et al., 2011, Dzhambov et al., 2017). The primary problem is that such a fixed measurement of noise exposure in most cases only includes noise outside the most exposed facade of members' houses. This results in some degree of misinterpretation of exposure levels. Residence-based noise exposure assessments are incapable of accurately measuring personal noise exposure because they do not take into account the actual geographical environment that people experienced. This is due to the fact that the majority of people participate in a variety of daily activities that take place outside of their

neighbourhood (Kwan, 2012). Previous research has ignored the space-time behaviour patterns of individuals as well as their exposure to environmental to non-residential circumstances. This has the potential to lead to inaccurate estimates of individual actual environmental factors, unreliable exposure–health relationships observed in statistical models, as well as misrepresentative research results (Brink, 2011, Park & Kwan, 2017, Kwan, 2018a, Kwan, 2018b, Tonne et al., 2018). Previous research has neglected to take into account the space-time behaviors of individuals as well as their exposures to non-residential contexts. This oversight has the potential to result in inaccurate estimates of person-specific actual environmental exposure, unreliable exposure–health relationships observed in statistical models, and misleading findings (Diaz & Pedrero, 2006, Kang et al., 2013) Because of this, it will be much simpler to conduct precise analyses of the relationships that exist between people's exposure to noise and their mental health. To this day, however, there has not been a sufficient amount of research conducted on personal noise exposure based on the space-time activities of individuals all over the world (Pirrera et al., 2010, Fallah-Shorshani et al., 2018, Tonne et al., 2018). Particularly in nations that are still in the process of industrialization, the increased noise pollution that is the result of rapid economic development has become a significant source of environmental and public health risk. The residents of megacities face a variety of challenges as a result of their place of residence. In recent years, towns have experienced a rapid increase in the population of both industries and vehicles, which has led to a significant increase in the amount of traffic, which has caused alarming levels of both noise and air pollution. Noise pollution is one of the problems that can put people's health and peaceful lives in jeopardy. Both marine and terrestrial ecosystems are vulnerable to the damaging effects of noise pollution. The effects of noise on one's health are one of the consequences of increased sound levels. The potential for communities to be negatively impacted by the noise pollution caused by road traffic is a significant environmental issue that needs to be addressed.

Scope of the Study

In this study, we will investigate whether or not there is a correlation between noise pollution and its effect on mental health. If a correlation is found, this study will also highlight the reasons for this correlation, as well as precautionary measures that can be taken to mitigate the negative effects of noise pollution. Additionally, both the short-term and the long-term effects of noise pollution on mental health will be investigated.

Objectives of the Study

1. The purpose of this study is to expose the current state of knowledge about noise's effects on mental health.
2. Through a review and critical analysis of the literature in order to identify the acquired knowledge and flaws, as well as to consider future research directions in terms of noise pollution.
3. This study aims to analyze and geo-visualize personal exposure to noise in various microenvironments based on individuals' space-time trajectories at an exceptionally fine resolution and to further investigate the relationships between mental health and personal noise exposure at both the activity/travel episode level and the entire day level.

If a link is found to exist between noise pollution and mental health as a result of this study, then the researchers behind this study will continue their investigation to determine the factors that led to the discovery of this link. This research will also be essential in recognizing the inherent dangers of noise pollution and the reasons why they continue to be unaddressed with regard to mental health.

Research Questions

1. Does noise pollution impact mental health?
2. What impacts does noise pollution have on mental health?
3. Does noise pollution have a long-term effect on mental health?
4. Can noise pollution cause permanent effects on mental health?

Significance of the Study

It has been discovered that people who have been subjected to noise pollution continue to be agitated, and the purpose of this search is to verify and evaluate the relationship between noise pollution and mental health.

The level of unsettling influence on the subjects' recognition, responsiveness, and execution was determined by subjecting them to varying decibel levels. According to the findings, chaos messes with people's memories, forces them to redirect their attention, and slows down their execution. The results of test reviews are the most widely known and account for half of the findings from the most recent audit (Pan, 2008).

The delayed repercussions of persistent urban lightning affect people of all ages, not just children. Several studies have found that being exposed to excessive noise can result in a variety of negative health effects, including anxiety, depression, hypertension, coronary disease, and stroke. An alarm signal is sent to the nerve center by the amygdala, which is a part of the brain that helps with the regulation of emotions, whenever a person is exposed to a disturbing noise. The nerve center immediately sends a message to the adrenal organs, which causes the adrenal organs to release adrenaline into the circulatory system. This is a learned response that allows individuals to react quickly in potentially dangerous situations (Navara & Nelson, 2007).

Adrenaline and another pressure chemical called cortisol are released in response to physiological changes. These changes include an increase in pulse rate and strain on the circulatory system. Because your body reacts so quickly, you frequently are unable to notice that these progressions have taken place (Larcher, 2022).

The commotion that is caused by humans has the potential to adversely affect a wide variety of creatures. Echo locating that, which urgently rely on sound for their action, may therefore serve as bioindicators to measure the effects that sound contamination has on the environment. Although there has been a lot of thought put into the effect that sound pollution has on the behaviour of creatures, very little is known about the effect that music has. We investigated whether music, particularly loud music, has an effect on the behaviour of that which is rummaging and drinking (Hasan & Jamal, 2021).

Noise Reaction Model

Babisch's noise reaction model defines the effects on the aural system by presentation to all levels of commotion such as hearing disability and tinnitus. This model is pivotal in terms of generating negative effects on wellbeing in this setting. Noise exposure hinders communication, aggravates day-to-day routine, and disturbs rest, leading to endocrine spiking and a number of mental and emotional retorts, as well as irritability, depression, and mental strain. In the event that the exposure continues for an extended period of time, the mental and emotional state of stress may cause a pathophysiological cascade, which may result in disturbed hormone levels, high blood pressure, and heart arrhythmias (Sewald, 2009).

Noise and Sleep Disturbance

There is evidence, both objective and subjective, that noise is disruptive to people's ability to get to sleep and stay asleep. An increased rate of change in the stages of rest and the number of arousals can be attributed to openness to commotion that disrupts sleep. This effect is proportional to the amount of commotion experienced. An increased number of sound openings are used during the evening and throughout the evenings in order to facilitate adjustment. Despite this, a study conducted by a research centre found no change in response to the highest possible level of noise exposure over the course of 14 nights. Oversleep agitation is probably going to happen if there are more than 50 different noise occurrences every night, each of which has a maximum level of at least 50 decibels A-weighted inside. In point of fact, there is not much of a correlation between the levels of outdoor noise and the degree of restlessness experienced (Conway, 2021).

An increase in blood pressure, heart rate, and finger pulse amplitude along with increased body movements may result from exposure to noise while sleeping. The perceived sleep quality, mood, and performance in terms of reaction time all decreased following sleep that was disrupted by road traffic noise. There may also be after-effects during the day following disturbed sleep. The amount of rapid eye movement (REM) sleep and slow wave sleep can both be increased if the indoor noise level is decreased, according to studies on noise abatement.8. It would appear that, although there may be some adaptation to sleep disturbance caused by noise,

complete habituation does not appear to occur, particularly for heart rate. This is particularly the case for those who were exposed to loud noises (Muzet, 2007).

Noise Exposure and Performance

Although this effect is not seen with non-speech noise, there is strong evidence, the majority of which comes from laboratory studies, that noise exposure impairs performance. This evidence suggests that performance may be impaired if speech is played while a subject reads and remembers verbal material. There is no correlation between the volume of the speech being referred to as "irrelevant" and the effects that it has. Reading, which is dependent on one's memory, may also be impaired because of how easily "irrelevant speech" can disrupt more complex mental tasks. This is because of how dependent reading is on one's memory (Loeb, et al., 1986).

It has been discovered that the perceived control over noise, as well as its predictability, plays an important role in determining the effects and after-effects of noise exposure. Glass and Singer discovered that tasks carried out in the presence of noise did not impair performance, but tasks carried out after the noise had been turned off did impair performance. This impairment was mitigated when subjects were given the perception that they had control over the noise. In point of fact, even the expectation of being subjected to loud noise in the absence of actual exposure can hinder performance, and the knowledge that one will be able to exert control mitigates this effect. The presence of noise can also slow down the rehearsal process in the memory, as well as influence the processes of selectivity in the memory and the choice of strategies for completing tasks. In addition, there is evidence that noise may decrease helping behaviour, increase aggressive behaviour, and decrease the processing of social cues that are seen as irrelevant to task performance (Glass et al., 1969).

Physiological Responses to Noise Exposure

The autonomic nervous system is responsible for mediating a number of predictable short-term physiological responses that occur in response to exposure to noise. An increase in heart rate and blood pressure, peripheral vasoconstriction, and ultimately an increase in peripheral vascular resistance are all symptoms of physiological activation that can be caused by prolonged exposure to noise. There is a rapid habituation to brief noise exposure, but there is less certainty that there will be habituation to prolonged noise exposure (De Boer, 1989).

Occupational Studies: Noise and High Blood Pressure

According to the findings of a number of occupational studies, people who are subjected to long-term, continuous noise at levels of at least 85 dB have been shown to have higher blood pressure than individuals who are not exposed to noise. In many of these studies, exposure to noise has also served as an indicator of exposure to other factors, both physical and psychosocial, that are also associated with high blood pressure (Melamed et al., 2001).

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

Methodology

For the purpose of my research, we will be gathering data and variables, and together we will develop a study protocol for the purpose of conducting a systematic review of studies that find a link between pollution and mental health. We will include observational studies (such as cohort studies, case-control analyses, and time series analyses) that investigate the associations between exposure to any type of pollution and the mental health of people aged 10 to 60. The symptoms that are associated with neurodevelopmental disorders, disruptive, impulse-control and conduct disorders, depressive disorders, anxiety disorders, substance disorders, and schizophrenia will be the primary outcome. The distribution of questionnaires is also going to be another method of data collection that will be used to determine the data that is necessary to produce results that are beneficial to the research. Random sample and sampling technique will be carried out to accomplishing the research objectives.

Results, Findings and Discussion

Demographic Profile

Age of Respondent					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	less than 18	11	10.3	10.3	10.3
	18-24	69	64.5	64.5	74.8
	25 and above	27	25.2	25.2	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

107 surveys were conducted and the results of those are as follows. People less than 18 were 11, people aged 18-24 are 69 followed by 25 and above are 27.

Gender of Respondent					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	male	52	48.6	48.6	48.6
	female	55	51.4	51.4	100.0
	Total	107	100.0	100.0	

107 surveys were conducted and the results of those are as follows. The population of men was 52 responses whereas the population of the female was 55. This constitutes men being 48.6 % of the entire sample size and women being 51.4 of the entire population size.

Graphical Analysis

Test Statistics ^a	
	Noise_pollution_on_mentalHealth
Mann-Whitney U	1300.500
Wilcoxon W	2840.500
Z	-.818
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.414

a. Grouping Variable: gender of respondent

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Noise_pollution_on _mentalHealth
Kruskal-Wallis H	.291
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.865

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: age of respondent

Descriptive Analysis

The data provided shows us that there is no significant difference in terms of noise pollution effects on mental health. However, when looking into the constructions we see that females are not satisfied with their mental health.

Reliability Analysis

The reliability statistics clearly define that .034 falls into the range of Cronbach alpha which shows the consistency in the survey conducted and shows the variables have a significant impact on the study.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based Standardized Items	Alpha on N of Items
.034	.273	12

Findings

Research conducted at the foundational level lends support that noise is a source of stress. The levels of stress hormones in the plasma, urine, and saliva of participants who were subjected to varying decibel levels of noise were measured by researchers. The following conclusions were arrived at by everyone in agreement: The levels of stress hormones in these three drinks were found to be significantly elevated. The effects of noise on memory, attention, and performance have been the subject of research conducted by researchers in experimental settings. In this experiment, human subjects were exposed to a range of decibel levels in order to determine the extent to which their memory, attention, and performance were affected by the noise. According to the findings, noise causes problems with memory, distracts attention, and lowers performance levels. The majority of the findings in this review came from experimental studies, which accounted for fifty percent of the total. In epidemiological research, the intellectual performance of students in noisy environments, as well as the intellectual performance of people living in locations near airports, trains, and highways, has been investigated. The findings indicate that students who attend schools with lower levels of noise have higher levels of academic success. Even when a person is asleep, their brain is constantly listening for any indications that they may be in danger. As a consequence of this, being exposed to excessive or loud noise can result in feelings of anxiety or stress. The longer a person is subjected to noise pollution, the more sensitive they become to the effects of stress. People who are exposed to excessive noise may become irritable, tense, frustrated, or angry. The effect on a person's mental health can be negatively impacted when that person believes they have no control over the level of noise in their surrounding environment.

Discussion

Karachi is one of the most important industrial cities in Pakistan; as a result of the expansion of Pakistan's industrial and transportation infrastructure, the city's residents may be subjected to increased levels of noise pollution. The objectives of this study were to (i) map the levels of noise pollution at various locations throughout Karachi; (ii) compare the levels of noise pollution in the morning, afternoon, and evening for each source; and (iii) assess the effects of noise on human health that are not audible to the human ear. In order to investigate the issue of noise pollution in Karachi, a sound level metre was placed in two factories as well as 43 popular or bustling areas for a period of twenty-four hours. In the vicinity of the sampling points, a survey that relied on questionnaires was conducted to elicit responses from the general public regarding the potential negative effects of noise pollution on one's health. At each of the sampling locations, in the morning, afternoon, and evening, the equivalent sound pressure levels (SPL_{eq}) that were measured were higher than the allowable limits. This was the case regardless of the time of day. During the afternoon shift at the Mian Muhammad Siddiq Textile Loom industry, the highest sound pressure level (SPL_{max}) measured 102 decibels inside the production unit. The average SPL was found to be 102 decibels on State Bank road, 101 decibels at Children's Hospital, and 100 decibels at Jhang Bazar in the afternoon, while it was 100 decibels in Karachi in the evening (97 dB). According to the findings of the survey, 94 percent of respondents experienced headaches, 76 percent had trouble sleeping, 74 percent suffered from hypertension, 74 percent experienced physiological stress, 64 percent had elevated blood pressure levels, and 60 percent felt dizzy as a result of noise. Noise pollution has reached levels that are above the recommended limits and is having adverse effects, both audible and otherwise, on humans. The workforce should be provided with soundproofing and protection equipment, and the vehicles and industrial machinery should be maintained in order to shield them from the extremely high levels of noise that they are exposed to on the job.

Conclusion

There are two topics that are covered multiple times throughout this test and deserve additional emphasis each time. The primary focus of this discussion is on the role that mental factors play in mediating the connection between commotion and human response, particularly with regard to the predictability, controllability, and significance of the commotion. The next topic addresses the possibility that the suppression of audible correspondence is to blame for a number of the effects that we have referred to as nonauditory effects. The conclusion suggests that the capacity to foresee and exert control over the occurrence of the clamour should intervene in both the mental and the physiological response. Consequently, unpredictable commotion is bound to upset execution, to prompt variable execution, to be detailed as irritating, and to be connected with neurotic reaction, then predictable clamour as one's discernment that a commotion is controllable, i.e., that it can be got away or stayed away from, can take out post-openness shortfalls in task execution and relational awareness. View of control likewise assume a part in detailed inconvenience and may be an ameliorative variable in commotion-initiated sickness. The perception that a respondent has of the function that noise plays in a given environment is an additional factor that plays a significant role in mediating the connection between noise and human response. There is reason to believe that these variables are also significant in predicting the effect of noise on performance as well as the neurotic reaction, despite the fact that the most solid data for this purpose are those gathered in noise irritation reviews. Despite the fact that we limited the scope of this article to discuss the effects of noise that are not audible, the fact that audible communication is hidden provides a 62 possible SHELDON clarification COHEN AND for a NEIL number WEINSTEIN of announced impacts, particularly the negative effects of noise on human performance. It should come as no surprise that a venture requiring audible interchanges as part of its exhibition will, by definition, be subject to extreme focus commotion. As was mentioned earlier, Poulton (1977) has also argued that even in situations where it is not obvious that someone is concealing themselves, noise can still make it difficult to gather subtle hearable feedback prompts or to hear one's own internal discourse. Covering of manager specialist or labourer correspondence may be partially responsible for increased frequency of accidents for those working in noisy modern settings. Clamor concealment of parent-child and instructor-child correspondence may also be responsible for the less fortunate

academic presentation among children who live in and also go to school in noisy neighbourhoods. It also seems logical that decreased social cooperations under clamour (e.g., Appleyard and Lintell, 1972) may be completely or partially due to one's anticipation that correspondence would be abnormal and difficult under loud conditions. This notion was presented in Appleyard and Lintell's study. In the aggregate, it is obvious that the mere presence of unwanted sound is not sufficient to cause an injurious impact of clamour. This is true even when the energies involved are generally concentrated. Our response to a particular issue is not predetermined in any way, and it is influenced in some way by its actual properties, its importance (counting its importance), and the various qualities of the respondent. When all things are considered, a general perspective on the current research suggests that prolonged exposure to high-intensity focus commotion in local community or work settings is frequently hazardous to the wellbeing and conduct of large portions of the population. . .

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